

Growing Inequality:
a Novel Integration of
transformations research

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D 9.4 GI-NI Ideas Lab Sessions Report

1 June 2022 & 5 March 2024

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1. Overview

In cooperation with the GI-NI consortium members, CEPS organised two dedicated GI-NI policy events. Both events took place in the context of the CEPS Ideas Lab.

CEPS Ideas Lab is an innovative platform for exchange and co-creation that brings together think-tanks, representatives of national governments, businesses, NGOs, and European institutions, to debate key political issues for Europe. This is an annual event organised in Brussels that brings together more than 1,000 high-level policy-makers, national representatives, renowned academics and the practitioners from the private sector. The aim of Ideas Lab is to provide a high level intellectual forum for exchanges concerning the wide range of current and pressing issues faced by the EU. CEPS Ideas Lab has long been at the forefront of fostering innovative discussions on Europe's most pressing issues, facilitating a unique intersection of policymakers, industry leaders, and academics.

The discussions are open, insightful and impactful with the active involvement of policy makers, researchers and representatives from industries and civil society. More information on the Ideas Lab can be found here: <https://ideaslab.ceps.eu/>

To use the stakeholder knowledge, the GI-NI consortium has specifically crafted the dissemination and communication strategy to maximise the expected as well as Dissemination and Impact WP9. In this strategy and WP, cooperation with stakeholder groups is made central. The consortium started the interaction and networking with stakeholders with CEPS Ideas Lab sessions which were held in June 2022 and March 2024. Views and feedback of the stakeholder will feed into future outputs. The GI-NI project will continue to create a platform where consortium can receive inputs for the upcoming deliverables and take their views into account.

The Ideas Lab sessions (D9.4 and Task 9.6) were organised by CEPS in cooperation with the consortium and Scientific Board Members Originally scheduled for January 2021 (M10), the first CEPS Ideas Lab was postponed due to the impact of COVID-19. Eventually, it took place on June 1st, 2022. GI-NI actively participated in the 9th and 11th editions of CEPS Ideas Labs, organising dedicated thematic policy sessions in 2022 and 2024. These sessions served as both dissemination opportunities and platforms for gathering feedback on the project's progress and policy directions. The CEPS Ideas Lab sessions contribute research-based insights and analytical depth to discussions, highlighting the critical role of evidence-based research in understanding and addressing the evolving dynamics of Europe's labour market. During both events, the GI-NI project has promoted itself with leaflets and a communication stand.

2. Outlines of the Ideas Lab Sessions

The summaries of two sessions can be found below.

- **Ideas Lab Session 1: Inequalities in the time of Covid, 1 June 2022**

As part of 9th edition of Ideas Lab, the first GI-NI policy event took place at the Square (Blue Point, Brussels). This session, structured as a 'lab' discussion, gathered approximately 27 participants, fostering accessible and interactive dialogue on the workshop's central theme. The aim was to kickstart a rigorous scientific debate, bringing together experts and policymakers to explore the topic of 'Inequalities in the Time of Covid.

The session focused on the impact of Covid-19 on income inequality and its interaction with other major trends such as globalisation and technological transformation, which are often considered responsible for increasing inequalities.

The speakers of the session were Giorgia Menta, Research Associate at LISER; Ivailo Kalfin, Managing Director of Eurofound; Michael Christl, Economic and Policy Analyst at the European Commission; Marcel Smolka, professor of International Economics at the University of Flensburg. The session was moderated by Cinzia Alcidi, Director of Research at CEPS. For wider reach, the entire session was recorded and made available online for interested parties to access (<https://vimeo.com/718744367>).

- **Ideas Lab Session 2: From unemployment battles to labour market shortages? 5 March 2024**

11th edition of Ideas Lab took place in person on 4 and 5 March 2024 at the Square (Mont des Arts, Brussels). The second GI-NI Ideas Lab session took place on 5 March 2024 with around 35 participants. The GI-NI lab was entitled “From unemployment battles to labour market shortages?”.

The session aimed to address the persistent issue of labour shortages in the current market landscape. Since the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and despite the economic slowdown driven by Russia's invasion of Ukraine, EU labour markets have demonstrated remarkable resilience. Employment reached a record high in 2022 and the trend is expected to continue, and most companies, in the EU and beyond, are grappling with major challenges in filling vacancies. Labour shortages in certain sectors and skills shortages in others is the new problem. The discussion centred on whether these shortages represent a transient phenomenon and queried whether unemployment remains a pervasive concern. Additionally, experts offered pragmatic insights into potential policy measures to mitigate these pressing challenges. This session, as part of a broader initiative to explore economic and social challenges in Europe, stood out as a testament to the Ideas Lab's commitment to deepening the understanding of labour market dynamics in a changing world.

The speakers of the session were Ekkehard Ernst, Chief of the Macroeconomic Policy and Jobs Unit at ILO, Malina Jankowska, Digital Public Sector Director at PwC CEE, Michael Handel, Professor at Northeastern University, , Majda Seghir, Researcher at Le CNAM , Ciresica Feyer, Deputy Head of Unit at DG reform, European Commission.

Photos From Ideas Lab Session 1: Inequalities in the time of Covid, 1 June 2022

**Photos from Ideas Lab Session 2: From unemployment battles to labour market shortages?,
5 March 2024**

GI-NI PROJECT IDENTITY

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Growing Inequality: a novel integration of transformations research — GI-NI

Coordinator

Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO, Netherlands

Consortium

CNAM – CEET, Centre d'études de l'emploi et du travail (France)
University of Groningen (Netherlands)
Centre for European Policy Studies (Belgium)
University of Adger (Norway)
Centre for Economic and Regional Studies (Hungary)
Utrecht University (Netherlands)
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